

RehabMove 2018: OXYGEN SATURATION PROFILE OF PARTICIPANTS OF THE 2017 BRAZILIAN SCHOLARSHIP PARALYMPIC GAMES

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PURPOSE: Pulse oximetry is one of the most common forms of monitoring in the critical care setting. Through a finger oximeter, it is possible to verify the presence of hypoxemia. The objective of this study was to verify the Heart Rate (HR) and the hemoglobin oxygen saturation (StO₂) in athletes participating in the 2017 Brazilian Scholarship Paralympic Games.

METHODS Participated in the study 49 male athletes of the CP Football (n=30) and Boccia Sports (n=19). The physiological variables heart rate (HR) and the hemoglobin oxygen saturation (StO₂) were measured at rest.

RESULTS: CP Football athletes presented 94.7±7.2 and 84.3±14.8 for %StO₂ and HR (bpm) respectively. On the other hand, to Boccia athletes was found values of 82.1±22.0 and 81.2±29.6 for %StO₂ and HR(bpm). Paralympic athletes, especially those with Cerebral Palsy (CP) can experience lower physical fitness levels which could undergo to oxygen desaturation. A possible explanation for this is that oxygen desaturation would be related to the VO₂max and the physical level of the athletes (MIYACHI, 1999).

CONCLUSIONS: In conclusion, athletes with CP has presented lower levels pf StO₂. Because it is a pioneering study in the area of Paralympic sport with athletes who present impairments (Cerebral Palsy and others), we realize the need for a special attention in their level of blood saturation, since the lack of oxygen in the blood can have relations to a training of high intensity that will lead to hyperventilation done wrong or inadequate.

Keywords: Disability. Oxygen Saturation of Hemoglobin. Heart rate. Cerebral Palsy.